

The Ideological Conflicts and their Effect on the Cultural Identity: Toni Morrison's Tar Baby

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Abstract

The ideology, identity, and culture conquer a great deal of attention in postcolonial studies. Understanding the nature of these concepts, how they work together, and how they are related to each other enable people to be aware of the ideological impacts of the West and consequently to decrease from these impacts. Abundant critical devotion to Morrison's 'Tar Baby' has been dedicated to enlightening the part that the original story played in the novel. Some critics have also regarded the novel as a humble defense of belief and tradition. Many other critics have concentrated on the cultural clash found in this novel as well as on Morrison's style of the naming of the characters and their impact on their self-identity. However, this study stresses the ideological conflicts and their influences on people's identity and culture, especially, the black ones. The researcher's goal is to display the ideological conflicts presented in Toni Morrison's Tar Baby to explore how the white ideology exerts influence on the black ideology and identity and how the white ideology causes ideological conflicts within the black people themselves and among them. The writer, here, employs the descriptive approach as a method of analysis of the selected data from the novel 'Tar Baby' depending on the theoretical framework of the postcolonial theory and Edward Said's theory of representing 'the Other'. Although the protagonists 'Jadine' and 'Son' loved each other and they belonged to the same nationality 'black American', they passed through a vast ideological conflict between them because of the impact of the white's ideology and culture on Jadine. At last, The white's ideology, identity, and culture won the battle against the black's ideology, identity, and culture.

Introduction

In the multicultural communities, especially the communities that contain the colonizer/colonized, Western/ non-Western, Self/ Other live together, the ideological conflict appears to the surface and this fact is highly illustrated by Morrison in her novel *Tar Baby*. Discourse, ideology, and identity are closely related to each other. The Western, through their discourses, tried hard to impose their supremacy, power, Knowledge, hegemony, and ideology on the non-Western. In recent times, we do not have a physical imperialistic in its exact meaning through war, but they impose their domination through imposing their ideology.

Toni Morrison is one of the most prominent African American novelists, who wins the Nobel and Pulitzer Prize. She has a lot of well-known novels among them are 'Song of Solomon,' 'Tar Baby', and 'Beloved'. Besides her being a famous novelist, she is also a well-known editor and professor. She established her own way of writing which is branded by the vivid thorough portrayals of Black Americans and their culture. She stresses also in her writings on the impact of exposing African Americans to the ideology and culture of the whites. Such impacts are the loss of the sense of belongingness and the imitation of the style of life of the other community and its culture or what is called 'Westernization'.

The name of the novel, *Tar Baby* originates from the Black American traditional story of the famous character of Brer Rabbit to 'Uncle Remus' the imaginary character and storyteller of a set of African American tales that are gathered and modified by Joel Chandler Harris and in the late 19th and early 20th century, he made this traditional story prominent. Linda Krumholz notices that "in most readings of *Tar Baby*, Brer Rabbit is associated with black people struggling against white domination, and the tar baby is a deception created by the white society that compels black people's complicity and entrapment" (2008, 274). Morrison created some modifications to this traditional tale and transfers it into a love story between Jadine and Son. Jadine, who is the tar baby, is an attractive African American model. She was extremely affected by white ideology and culture. Son, who is the rabbit imprisoned by the tar baby, is a representative African American criminal that stayed faithful to his African American ideology and culture.

In *Tar Baby*, We have the fundamental ideological conflict between the white and the black which represents the ideological conflict between the Self/ Other or Western/ non-Western. As a result of this continuous conflict, we have the inner ideological conflict which takes place within the protagonists, Jadine, and Son, themselves.

Methodology

The current paper is qualitative library-based research and a descriptive-analytical one. The objective of this paper is to read the *Tar Baby* novel written by Morrison. The theoretical framework of the study depends on Edward Said's ideas about the Self/ the Other, Applying the ideas of Said on Morrison's selected novel is an attempt to explain the way by which the white ideology affects the ideology of the black due to the ideological conflicts that arise in the blacks' self-identities.

Literature Review

Many critics have written about the novel 'Tar Baby'. One of them is Goyal. In her article "*The Gender of Diaspora in Toni Morrison's Tar Baby*" she maintained that "neither can be upheld as a reliable authority on race or gender, as Morrison uses the two to displace the other's certainties and to reveal their limitations" (2006, 406). Moreover, in her essay "*Blackness and Art in Toni Morrison's 'Tar Baby'*", Krumholz claimed, "that Morrison connects certain aesthetic choices in *Tar Baby* to blackness"(2008, 267). Ravichand, also in his article "*The Experience of Culture Clash in Toni Morrison's Tar Baby*", endeavors to "show how capitalism plays an important role in giving birth to some of the devastating prejudices in a racial capitalistic American society, and how people constantly fall into its trap to fit themselves into its skillfully structured system, just to make their life more miserable"(2013, 9). Furthermore, in the essay "*Sealskins and Original Dimes: Exploitation, Class, and Commodity Fetishism in Toni Morrison's Tar Baby*" Lutz attempted to give "the novel's overt concern with the connection between exploitation and commodity consumption, along with its attention to class structures that reinforce social and economic domination"(2013, 57). In this article, the researcher endeavors to unearth the enormous impact of the whites' ideology on the ideology of the blacks who are in constant contact with them and the vast ideological conflict of the blacks resulted from such contact.

1. Discussion

1.1.The ideological conflict between the White and the Black

According to Edward Said, no one can flee from dealing with West/East, Self/ Other, White/ Black, and Powerful/ powerless divisions. We cannot come across these divisions by acting as if they are not existed or real (1979, 327). Said believes that there is no escape from being on one side of the binary oppositions, either being the Western or the non-Western, being either the White or the Black, and either being the Powerful or the Powerless. For Said, the individual works of the novelists are shown as part of the relationship between culture and empire (1994, xxii). He thinks that the responsibility of the novelists, through their writing, is to display the relationship between colonialism with its all weapons such as ideology, culture, and identity and the ideology and culture of the colonized people. The Westerners want to ensure their superiority by spreading their ideology, identity, and culture. From their perspective, they regard their ideology, identity, and culture as the dominant one. Through their discourse, the Western asserts their supremacy and hegemony over the non-Western, they depend on employing the binary oppositions and stereotyping to differentiate between them and the non-Western. As Said stresses that "Orient" and "Occident" are artificial and man-made. Moreover, the connectionbetween them is a connectionof power, of dominance, and of variabledegrees of a complicatedhegemony (1979, 5).Orientalism, therefore, is a created body of theory and practice in which there has been a considerable material investment. Continued investment made Orientalism, as a system of knowledge about the Orient, an accepted grid for filtering through the Orient into Western consciousness (Said, 1979, 6).

Van Dijk's contends that "ideologies consist of social representations that define the social identity of a group, that is, its shared beliefs about its fundamental conditions and ways of existence and reproduction". Therefore, For him, ideologies have social functions through discourses, to guide the social practices, actions and interactions of a certain social group's members. Evidently, that the discourses are instrumental to cumulatively build narratives within ideologies through language and other social semiotic vehicles, making them so banal and ubiquitous (2006, 116). Fairclough explains that language is a social practice that articulates a dialectical, ideological relationship between discourse and various social structures (political, social, economic). Whereby, ideological 'discourse is shaped by structures, but also contributes to shaping and reshaping them' (1995, 73).

Binary is a notion in structuralism which is not merely imbedded in Saussure's linguistics but as well as in the cultural anthropology of Radcliffe-Brown, it aids to describe the process of creating meaning in one word or symbol by making reference to another reciprocally private word. The two words may be perceived to define a whole system, by referring to two basic positions in which the components of that system can occur, for instance (culture/nature; dark/light; male/female; birth/death). One part of the binary opposition can have significance merely with regard to the other part. Each part has the implication of being its corresponding. A

word may possibly consequently appear in more than a single binary opposition, with being adapted appropriately to its meaning. In any system of symbols, definite binary oppositions can be grasped to determine the relationships to each other (Edgar and Peter, 1999, 28). The analysis of the pairs of binary oppositions offers an essential understanding about how an ideology works. Ideology might therefore function accurately to the extent that such pairs of binary oppositions are taken for granted, seeming to reflect more willingly than to organize the world. The criticism that are directed towards ideology requires the explanation of a series of binary oppositions as a culturally precise explanation, picking and preferring of components from the surrounding world (Edger and Peter, 1999, 29).

According to the binary oppositions, the entire novel *'Tar Baby'* can be divided into the White/ Black world as well as the two main protagonists who represent two different ideologies and cultural concepts of these two worlds, although the protagonists are both African Americans. The first world contained the following group of people: Mr. Valerian Street who is a wealthy sweet manufacturer from Philadelphia. He was spending the money that he got from his retirement fund in 'the Isle des Chevaliers' and Mrs. Margaret Street who is Valerian's wife and who was the previous Miss of Maine. They represented the White American community. While 'Gideon' and 'Therese' are the native Americans who lived on the island, Gideon worked as an orchard man for the Street's family and 'Therese' worked as a washerwoman for the Street's. They return to the Black American community with the protagonist 'Son' who is roaming from one place to another for his killing his wife and her beloved. Then, after he killed her and her beloved, he ran away from the ship where he worked in to 'the Isle des Chevaliers'. It is the place in which he started living after his finding as a visitor. Son is regarded as the representative figure of the Black world.

Amongst these two opposite poles, there is the shadow that is comprised of white and black, the shadow people didn't belong to the white or the black. These shadow people are the Childs' family who represented by 'Sydney' and his wife 'Ondine' who are the nearest to the black society and they are full of pride for being as they described themselves as 'Philadelphia Negro' who functioned as a servant and a cook for the Streets', practically managing their house. They isolated themselves from the other people who lived near them. They even stayed away from the other Black families like Gideon & Therese's family because the Childs' family considers itself superior to other Black families because they have been affected by whites' ideology and culture and they have acquired many principles from being exposed to the white's ideology and culture, therefore they aren't regarded as pure members of the black society by the researcher but as a mixture from the white society and the black society since they are fell under the influence of white ideology and culture which is represented by their owners. They lost everything by leaving their racial heritage and they neither belong to the whites nor the blacks (Flohr,10). However, the person who is immersed in the white ideology and culture is Jadine, the Childs' niece, who had been with them from the time when her father and mother had passed away in her infancy. As a result of being raised in the Valerian Streets' house, and Valerian paid for her education, she became very successful in the white community, particularly in the field of beauty. Her success is obviously seen by the appearance of her picture as a fashion model on the cover page of *Elle's* magazine. This point is further confirmed by the Parisian man's proposal to marry Jadine. She is the representative figure of the White World.

From the first glance of the novel, the apparent associations between the representative figures of the white & black worlds, which represented by Jadine and Son, in the house of Mr. Valerian Street are superficially stable. But with finding Son in Margaret Street's closet, the tensions between these two worlds appeared to the surface. As a result of this tension, the poorly balanced system of the Street's house change into chaos. Sydney, Ondine, and Margaret depicted Son racially as 'the Other', they distrusted him at all and wanted to compel him not to stay in the house. Furthermore, Sydney even suggested to shoot him. The treatment of Son as the 'Other' which was used by Margaret, Sydney, and Ondine is very obvious, they didn't trust him and they attempted to dismiss him from the Streets' house although, he practically did nothing, just they found him hiding in Margaret's closet. They treated him as different from them although, they belong to the same race and culture. Moreover, The Childs hardly tried to adjust themselves with Son's existence and with his status as a visitor to Valerian, since being a guest enabled him to sleep near to his steward in the white part of the house which is specialized to the visitors while the Childs ought to stay in the servant's part. They served the Streets for a long time but they never allowed to sleep in the white part near their masters. Therefore, they felt jealous of Son. He was perceived as an offense to his race by the Childs. Valerian, as an opposition to his wife's agitated actions throughout Son's finding, requested Son to remain in his house till he could make his preparations to get back to the United States. He showed his disrespect for the Childs' aggressiveness and Jadine's conflicting reaction to Son since he belongs to their people. The rising battle between Son and Jadine turned to be a battle about attempting to impose his/ her ideology and culture on the other. Son performed as Jadine's rival, standing for the traditional black heritage, whereas Jadine is the contemporary Anglo-American woman.

Here, in the *Tar Baby*, one can notice in their first encounter, the question of belongingness came up. Belongingness or what is called the social identity denotes to the way by which a person describes himself or herself as a member of a specific social class. Thus, as Pitonyak declares that "social identity is something that

links us to the social world and provides the pivot between the individual and society" (2002, 7). The notion of belongingness is regarded as an important subject in many varied fields of studies such as culture, literature and many other disciplines. The sense of belongingness has an integral part in recognizing of how a person is able to provide meaning to his or her life. One's self identity is formed on the basis of the social relations that illustrate his/her connection to definite class through having principles, beliefs, or activities in common. Hagerty, in his article, links the feeling of belongingness to "the experience of personal involvement in a system or environment so that persons feel themselves to be an integral part of that system or environment" (2002, 794). He indicated that the feeling of belongingness may arise from the relations that we create with individuals, places, social classes, societies, and cultures. Moreover, Deci and Ryan propose that the necessity for being belonged or related to a certain group "encompasses a person's striving to relate to and care for others, to feel that those others are relating authentically to one's self, and to feel a satisfying and coherent involvement with the social world more generally" (1991, 243). Therefore, the feeling of belongingness is quite significant, it may be regarded as one of the most vital requirements of human being because without the feeling of relatedness and belongingness, one may feel neglected and useless and his whole life is aimless.

When Jadine termed herself and the entire members of the Street house with the pronoun 'us', this done stimulated Son to inquire her: "Us? You call yourself 'us'? . . . But you . . . you're not a member of the family. I mean you don't belong to anybody here, do you?" (Morrison, 1981, 118). And Jadine's response was: "I belong to me. But I live here" (Morrison, 1981, 118). As Said declares in his book *'Culture and Imperialism'* that by the passing of time, culture turns to be aggressively connected with nations or states. The difference between 'us' and 'them' is always connected with what is called xenophobia (1994, xiii). This binary opposition of "Us" and "Them" which is used by Jadine here made Son ask her "Us? You call yourself 'us' ". He is astonished by her employment of the pronoun 'us' who is specialized only for the white. Then he reminded her that she is not a member of the Streets' family, on the contrary, she is from the member of the Childs who is the Streets' African servants. Her answer to Son was she belonged to herself only. Here, the sense of her loss of identity is very obvious, firstly, she said that she is white, as she considered herself as one of the Streets' family, then she said that she belonged to herself only and she did not even mention her origin or the Childs because they are her remaining relatives. Here the sense of loss of the cultural identity for Jadine is very clear as a result of her attachment to the ideology and culture of the white and her neglecting her ideology and culture which is the African American one. After this conversation between them, and because she lost her cultural identity, she related her identity to the people to whom she worked, she told him that she is working for Margaret Street as her private secretary and later on she mentioned the Childs who is her real relatives. The shifting of her identity from Streets' identity to her own identity to the Childs' identity is very important to show that she has no stable identity at all. For Jadine, culture is a sort of theatre in which many elements, such as ideology and politics, influenced and are involved in each other. As Said says that "In this second sense culture is a sort of theater where various political and ideological causes engage one another. Far from being a placid realm of Apollonian gentility, culture can even be a battleground on which causes expose themselves to the light of day and contend with one another"(1994, xiii). While for Son, Culture is identity, so his identity came from the culture to which he belonged. As Said states that culture, here, considered as a powerful source for identity, and even we can say that it is a combative source due to what has been seen in modern 'returns' to tradition and culture (1994, xiii).

In this novel, we have the performance of the stereotype of the black man that is used by the white to express their ideology that is the superior one as opposite to the ideology of the black which is inferior. The concept of stereotype is a wide, often oversimplified supposition made about all the individuals of a certain group. Stereotypes are features enforced upon sets of people due to their race, nations, and sexual trends. These features incline to be oversimplifications of the sets concerned, and where some people really do exemplify the features of their stereotype, they are not essentially representative of all the members in that group. Stereotypes are not permanently precise and even though they are positive, they may be harmful (Hall, 1997, 249). Lippmann describes "stereotype" as a "distorted picture or image in a person's mind, not based on personal experience, but derived culturally" (1998, xvii). For Lippmann, "Stereotypes are seen as dependent on cultural traditions, group interests, and the differentiation of the in-group from outsiders (1998, xxv)". Lippmann debates that the construction of stereotypes is led by social, cultural, political, and economic motives, and when they are handed over from a generation to the other, they may turn to be quite prevalent and unwilling to change.

These stereotypes of the black man, that are found in the novel, are as follows: the stereotype of the criminal, sexual, and primitive black man. The stereotype of the criminality of the black man was presented through: firstly, the way by which Son was presented to Valerian's house, This presentation was with a gun at his back. Secondly, jumping from the ship and existing on the island for many days, and finally, he was frowzy and muddy. All these features are the exact depiction of the criminal according to the white perspective "a black man with dreadlock hair" (Morrison, 1981, 80). As well as the stereotype of the sexuality of the black man, this stereotype was presented through the accusing of Son in attempting to rape Margaret and Jadine, firstly, just because Son had been found in Margaret's closet, he is accused in attempting to rape her and secondly, just because of his looks at her, Jadine accused him also in trying to rape her, "corresponding to his – in her eyes –

uncivilized looks, and accuses him of attempted rape" (Morrison, 1981, 121). Son's reaction towards this general supposition and stereotype was, "Why you little white girls always think somebody's trying to rape you?" (Morrison, 1981, 121), and this question can be asked to every white woman who thinks and believes in this stereotype. Finally, the stereotype of the dangerous, aggressive, and primitive black man, Once, Son came into Jadine's room for the first time, she regarded him as wild, aggressive, and uncivilized man and she described his hair as "chain gang hair,hair that needed to be put in jail" (Morrison, 1981, 113). Later on, she treated him as a stupid, uneducated, illiterate "nigger" (Morrison, 1981, 123) and by questioning him if he understood the meaning of the word "patron" (Morrison, 1981, 118). When she was motivated by his manners and she named him "ape" (Morrison, 1981, 121). By using these stereotypes of the criminal, sexual, and primitive black man. It is clear that she places herself in the group of white society, she completely forgot her black heritage and background.

Thus, by employing binary oppositions and stereotyping against the Black in *Tar Baby*, the whites try to sustain their ideology which they regard it as the most acceptable, respectable, attractive, and influential one. At the same time, they attempt to weaken the other ideologies to assert their hegemony on the blacks even in their ideology.

1.2. The inner ideological conflicts of the protagonists

The entire novel, as we said earlier, may be divided into two worlds: The New York World which stands for the white ideology and culture to which Jadine belongs now and The Elloe World which stands for the black ideology and culture to which Son belongs. The contrast between the two worlds is extremely enormous. The attempt of the two main protagonists to make the other adjust to his world started when each one took the other to visit his/her world. The experience was very conflicting difficult, and astonishing to them.

Jadine is an example of the black woman who was greatly influenced by the Western ideology and culture and she completely lost her cultural identity in terms of her black origin, she was related to her extraordinary physical beauty, that is flourished with the help of the well-paid occupation in the modeling industry, rather than to be related to her place of birth and her ancestors. She conducted her life as a white woman, she forgot that she is a black woman because she had been brought up and educated with the financially supported by Valerian Street. Son Green is an example of an African American stowaway who highly appreciated his black ideology and culture and he started roaming from one place to another after his killing of his wife 'Cheyenne'. He followed Jadine in secret from the ship to Mr. Valerian Street's house where he concealed in the wardrobe of Mrs. Margaret.

We can say that Jadine is suffering from the concept of assimilation which refers to the approval of the adoption of the Westerners' style of life by the non-Westerners when they come to live in the West. Westernization may be regarded as a kind of assimilation that may be practiced by the non-Westerners towards the dominant and hegemonic culture of the West. Jadine has changed her life in accordance to the life of the whites due to her closeness to the whites' ideology and culture. She underwent from the process of assimilation as a result of her influenced by the Western's culture and ideology. She lived her life as a white woman. She is also a victim of Westernization through her living as the white's style of life because of her job with the whites and her white educational institution that she studied in. When Son met Jadine, he regarded her as a white woman regardless of the fact that she belongs to the people of the black skin. Yuh-Chuan asserts in his article that "Jadine thinks and conducts herself like a white, and her whiteness stands out as the legacy of white education and way of living" (2006, 559). Son regarded her to be a white woman; however, it may be said that she was a black girl who possessed a white culture and ideology. Therefore, she thought of herself as being a young white woman until she encountered Son. Here is the crucial moment in her life where her inner ideological conflict was started. In the past, she forgot or willing to forget her authentic cultural identity, but from the first moment when she met Son, she began to think about her original identity as a black girl. Because of her sexual appealed to him, as well as the point that he didn't belong to her new environmental world that she is well familiar with now, and he didn't care at all about many things that she is distinguished with. All these things gave rise to Jadine to rethink about her new ideology and identity. She suddenly found herself preoccupied with the sense of belongingness, she at once started feeling that she biologically belonged to the black world. Therefore, she was visited by images of her original identity and situations that are related to her childhood. At Street's house, she was living in a way that is compatible with her breeding and her education, nonetheless, her confronting with Son stormed inside her the feeling of discomfort, and then as Audi declares that it is "fragmentation" as he calls it (2000, 10). Jadine is "drifting, in trouble, [with a] desire to 'make it' that may be self-destructive" (Kirkpatrick, 2010, 33). After meeting with Son, Jadine fall in love with him. Later on, she essentially started living in an inner conflict. Suddenly, she found herself, didn't belong to whom she was thinking for years to belong and she was always acted as being one of them and she lived on that basis with self-respect and self-satisfaction, and she is unwilling to be reconnected with her original identity which is inferior to her adopted one, she was not ready to lose all the success that she reached in her job. Jadine lived in conflict with herself, she was torn up between her acquired identity as an educated fashion model who is highly influenced by white ideology and culture on one hand, and on the other hand, and between her original identity

as a black woman that had been destroyed by the elegance life of the whites. As a result of that, Jadine's attempt to draw Son to her white ideology and culture.

As far as Son is concerned, he was very attached to his black ideology and culture as well as with his place Eloe, Florida, where he was born. In Son's first visit to Jadine's room, he realized that Jadine was on the cover. Then, he was frightened by her luxurious life that she dwelled in, he saw her sealskin overcoat, her silk apparel, and her gold-thread foot wears. At this moment, Son realized that Jadine conducts her life in a whitish style as well as he realized the huge gap between him and her concerning her lifestyle, her ideology, and her culture. About this sealskin overcoat, it was given to her as an expensive Christmas gift from her French white fiancé. The overcoat was made from the skin of seals' babies that sewed together in an attractive way. And she liked it so much. From the situation of the overcoat, it is clear to what extent that she is influenced by the whites and their tremendous wealth. Metaphorically speaking, she was fond of such sort of black sealskin. Elizabeth House asserts that Jadine reveals that "her lack of altruism through wearing apparel" (1984, 199). The overcoat, that was found in her chamber, embodied her own skin. Jadine identified herself with the overcoat. The overcoat is a black one just like her and it is created by the white people, just like Jadine herself who is raised to be white by white people. Therefore, the overcoat precisely represented Jadine because she is also black and she, metaphorically speaking, is created by the whites.

For Son, Jadine's visions were associated with the white principles, values, and culture that gave her the material thoughts of prosperity that she is eager for, consequently, he perceived her as a white girl despite the fact that she is a black girl (Havlíková, 2013, 15). Son wanted her to have dreams like a black woman whose dreams were connected with having a yellow house with white entrances that the black women used to open their white entrances and they started chatting with each other and invited each other to their house: "Come on in, you honey you!" (Morrison, 1981, 119). Son wished that Jadine is being able to be as a black woman with all that he knew about the true black woman. Quite the reverse, she wished that he is being able to acquire an education and a job and she hoped that they will have the same dreams. But she was discouraged by his full rejection to return to school and to attempt to look for an occupation.

Later on, she started to be conscious about the reason behind his rejection is that he was aware that she tried to pull him deeper into her new white world and he resisted her attempt to bring him to her new world. Her new consciousness began to impact her and her behavior with him. During his visit to New York, Son started dwelling with her after the spectacular burst of stress between them in *L'Arbe de la Croix* in the course of the house's Christmas celebration, Jadine began to feel that she might be succeeded in New York City because the people of the city treated her well and respected her but Son's impression was completely different.

Here, it is clear that Jadine's ideology is not pure one because of her contact with the whites since she is a black girl while Son's ideology is pure one since he remained faithful to his culture and beliefs. From Son's viewpoint, New York was not a safe place for black people. Women seemed to be split apart by their attempts to satisfy different concepts of beauty. Men as well became paying less attention to their women. Besides, the eminent differences, that appeared in his life after meeting Jadine, seemed to turn his life into blurry and as a result of this blurriness, Son began to feel in pain and sorrow (Flohr,8). Son was feeling very sorry and grief for the black people who changed their life in accordance to the life of the whites due to their closeness to the whites' ideology and culture just like Jadine. Such people were subjected to the process of assimilation. The result of this process is Westernization that the black people act or imitate the life style of the whites. Son attempted some kind of television, but the blacks who are acting as if they are whites made him crazy, even their skin had altered by the help of the white ideology and culture as the color television which changed the black and white pictures into color pictures. He is deeply confused about whether those black people are right or he is right. Whether the black people, who are influenced by Western ideology and culture, are the correct or those who stay adheres to their cultural heritage. One has to keep up with the times, and keep pace with the developments of the Western and follow the white ideology, or one has to be honest and loyal to his past, and remain stick to his ideology that what made Son puzzled and conflicted.

Son's experience in New York was the strongest clash for him with Jadine and her cultural and ideological beliefs. He noticed that her ideological and cultural beliefs are formed from a mixture of whites and blacks' beliefs, he discovered that she lived in a highly ambivalent life that he greatly suffered to grasp. Son could not adjust himself to the different environment that he found himself in. Instead, he determined to return to his birthplace 'Eloe' as well as to return to the appearances of his ideological and cultural principles. Here, the contrast between him and Jadine is clear, he had a great spirit of belongingness to his origin, on the opposite of her totally. Therefore, he insisted on taking her to his homeland so as to live and to experience how to live like a black woman among black people, as an attempt from him to return her to her origin and to start feeling the sense of belongingness. As he went with her to New York and experienced how to live like a white man among white people. Now, it is her turn to experience living in a black community. When Jadine finally agreed on his plans, therefore, now it's her turn to go through culture and ideological conflict.

As far as Jadine is concerned, her style of life was dependent on the place where she lived in now and on her professional and educational background not on the place where she came from. That means she had suffered from Westernization by living her life as the white's style of life because of her job with the whites and her white educational institution that she studied in, she became a victim of Westernization. As a result of being subjected to the process of Westernization, Jadine is apparently an American fashion model with a black skin but her actions and behaviors are definitely white. Her professional and educational background illustrates to which extent that her identity and her ideology are affected by the current place that she is living in now, not by her birthplace that she came from. This contradiction was very evident, especially when Therese told Son that she is unable to remember her "ancient properties" (Morrison, 1981, 305). From this conversation, it is obvious that Jadine is missing all her ties with her black inheritance and she lost her sense of belonging with her origin because she was highly attached to the whites' ideology and culture. Her returning to Paris so as to be as near as possible to Ryk revealed her powerful longing for being thoroughly linked to the white ideology and culture. As stated by Audi, Jadine was not been able to live her personal life with no hope that she has the opportunity of getting an integrated self (2000, 21).

In the same way, Son took Jadine to see his world 'Eloe's'. When they arrived there, they met the first people of the black society, she was astonished to discover that she came into a place that gives a priority to the splitting-up between males and females. When Son was talking to the men, she had to stay and talk to the women with whom she did not have anything in common to talk about. For her, furthermore, it is hard to be related to such women with such a conservative society. That means she had lost all the ties that connect her with her race as well as she has lost the feeling of belongingness with her original society, therefore, she got rid of the discussion with them ten just after ten minutes from its beginning. Son hoped that Jadine can easily comprehend and change her behavior compatible with her new different situations, requirements, and novelties. From the time when he came across her unintentionally through his first existence in the Streets' family, he started his effort to handle her dreams as well as to change her dreams to be as similar as to his dreams so that she can dream in things that he would like her to dream in like having a yellow house that has white entrances.

Son's understanding of the role of women was in the very traditional one, he dreamed of women who take care of their children, manage their church life, and do their house works. His advance dreams about Jadine's ability to get attacked or harmed as well as his part as the protector that is able to protect her and without him she will die, like such dreams that entertained him so much in New York. But unfortunately, Jadine does not like this kind of dreams that he likes her to have. As a substitute, Jadine was preoccupied with the frightening dream that she first went through in Eloe practically as a response to her wrath about the sex-separation as well as the ethical rules of the society. In this frightening dream that she received a set of black women including Therese and Ondine, they wandered into her room and showed her their breasts. These "night women", as Jadine called them, made her feel endangered especially in the matter of confirming their femininity. They didn't believe her assertion that she also has breasts, there is a reference here that she is not considered a woman from the black woman's perspective, their doubt, that she is a woman like them, implies that they didn't regard her sexy like them. Their breasts are the embodiment and the symbol of their womanhood which is highly different from Jadine's.

The woman with the yellow costume was similar to everyone in the store, but Jadine became motionless with astonishment by the presence of this woman that was completely different from her. Although this woman did not act under the Western idea of beauty, she made Jadine gasp. This woman with the yellow costume was depicted as a woman's woman. She was also depicted as having incredible beauty. The woman with the yellow costume, who is an African American woman, is the real representation of womanhood and beauty rather than Jadine who is regarded as a model and fashion model from the perspective of the white. Jadine was influenced by her and followed her but she spat on Jadine's face.

After the frightening dream and the humiliation situation of the woman with the yellow costume in Paris, Jadine started feeling isolated, unreal, and puzzled. Therefore, she left Paris to search for a shelter in L'Arbe de la Croix. Even there, she was confronted with the black concept of the role of the woman and just a few hours before she returned to Paris, Ondine directed her that all she needs is to take care of the people who are older than her. The daughter means a woman who pays attention to the place from where she came from and looks after the old people there. But Jadine doesn't and can't accept this notion of a woman. She didn't want to be that type of woman that Ondine talked about. She thought that there are many other means to become a woman rather than taking care of the old people of her place.

The concept of femininity and being sexual from the black women's perspective and the real representation of womanhood and beauty from their perspective, too, increased Jadine's ideological conflict. She has been ideologically shaken by the night women as well as by the woman with the yellow costume. As she used to be familiar with the contemporary style of the fashion centers all over Europe and the USA, but now she felt that she is disgracefully imprisoned when she was living with the black community in Paris. This imprisonment presented an apparent divergence in her life. At this point, Morrison highlights that when Jadine returned to Isle des Chevaliers, she returned with a complete state of ideologically shock. she no longer knew

whether she is a white woman or a black woman now. She felt that she is no longer belong to this place. She was related with it when she was still a black woman but now she is another one, she is a black girl with a white face.

Thus, Son's ideological conflict led him, at last, to commit his crime in raping Jadine and the writer, here, thinks that when he raped her, he was convinced that she is a white girl, not Jadine the black one and she is no longer belong to the black race. The moment of Son's raping Jadine can be regarded as the climax of his inner ideological conflict. It is clear, here, that to what extent the effect of the ideological conflict may be and to what extent it may be very severe on people to whom it is subjected, it urges them to do things they do not even believe in. Because of his inner ideological conflict, Son raped the girl to whom he loved and to whom he wanted to marry. When he returned four hours later, after raping Jadine, he was remorseful and frightened that he had gone too far in raping Jadine. During their last dialogue, Jadine was wearing only a T-shirt, which encouraged Son to describe her as "the Cheech and Chong T-shirt was up around her waist and her nakedness below embarrassed him now. He had produced that nakedness and having soiled it, it shamed him" (Morrison, 1981, 272). It is obvious that Son overpassed the climax of his internal ideological conflict by raping Jadine, he felt regret for his wicked action, and now he is in a state of reconciliation with himself. He began to feel that he loves her and needs her, therefore he followed her to the Isle des Chevaliers and he stayed with her again. By returning to Jadine, This illustrates that Son accepted the western ideology and accepted to be just like Jadine because he loves her.

Conclusion

In *Tar Baby*, there is the ideological conflict between the whites who are represented by the white Americans and the Blacks who are represented by the black Americans. This ideological conflict resulted from the attempt of the whites to assert that their ideology and culture is superior than the ideology and culture of the blacks. Their assertion comes from their employing certain instruments such as representing the Other through using binary opposition and stereotyping the Other.

Through the employment of the binary oppositions, the entire novel '*Tar Baby*' can be divided into the White/ Black world. Between these two opposite poles, there is a group of blacks who were the victims of such ideological conflict. These people are represented by the Child's family in this novel. This family is working as servants at the white man's house 'Mr. Street'. They may be called as the shadow people who are comprised from whites and blacks' ideologies. These shadow people didn't belong to the whites or the blacks. They have been affected by whites' ideology and culture and they have acquired many principles from being exposed to the white's ideology and culture, therefore they aren't regarded as pure members of the black society by the researcher but as a mixture from the white society and the black society since they are fell under the influence of white ideology and culture which is represented by their owners. Because of the ideological conflict between the white and the black, these people lost everything and they became neither belong to the whites nor the blacks (Flohr,10). However, the person who was highly immersed in the white ideology and culture is Jadine, the Childs' niece. One can see from the first encounter between Jadine and Son that she loses the sense of belongingness with the black community and the sense of her loss of the black identity is very obvious. The shifting of her identity from Streets' identity to her own identity to the Childs' identity is very important to show that she has no stable identity at all. The stereotypes of the black man that are used by the whites in the novel are the stereotype of the criminal, sexual, and primitive black man.

There is also the inner ideological conflict that the two protagonists, Jadine who stands for the white ideology and Son who stands for the Black ideology, suffered from. As a consequence of this ideological conflict, we have a very harsh impact on the cultural identity of the protagonists. Jadine was a victim of the process of Westernization. An enormous influence on Jadine's progress is her European white education. She is a successful fashion model who was highly influenced by the whites and their ideology and culture. This shows her inner conflict as she wanted to live her free life just like a white American woman, not as a black woman. Jadine Childs whose subjectivities are divided between a wish to assimilate to the culture and ideology of the whites and a voice that urges her to return to the culture and ideology of her ancestor 'the black'. Her experience in Eloë was very hard for her and was the strongest clash with Son's cultural and ideological background which she discovered so hard to adjust.

On the contrary, Son is very involved with his African American ideology and culture as well as with his place Eloë, Florida, where he was born. He is very stick to his ideology and culture, he had a very strong sense of belonging. After encountering Jadine, he feels attracted to her, but unfortunately, during the first meeting with her in her room, he discovers that she is more white woman than being black woman. Even her dreams are associated with white culture and values. Because he loves her, he accepts to go with her to New York. Son's experience in New York was very hard for him and was the strongest clash with Jadine's cultural and ideological background which he discovers so hard to understand. Son cannot change himself to the new and different surroundings that he discovers himself in. But, he rather determined on his birthplace 'Eloë' as well as the appearances of his cultural and ideological principles.

Each one of them, Jadine and Son, insists on her/his world's ideological point of view. Jadine insists on following the white ideology and culture and Son insists on following the black ideology and culture. Therefore, each one of them did his/ her best to force his/ her to follow the ideology to which he/ she belongs motivated by their love for each other. After Jadine's rape by Son, they thought that everything is ended, therefore Jadine returned to France to start her life that she departed in bewilderment, while Son is led into the legendary presence among the sightless horsemen that still dwell on the Isle des Chevaliers. But the writer, here, thinks that Jadine, at last, wins the battle because she stayed just as loyal and faithful to her white ideology and culture, but Son's returning to look for Jadine means that he surrendered to the white ideology and culture. Therefore, at last, white ideology and culture success the clash against the black ideology and culture. Morrison, in this novel, endeavored to display the sturdy influence of the Western ideology and culture on young black people.

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